

Advancing Immune Defense of Pancreatic β -Cells through Innovative Tissue Engineering Scaffolds

Version 1

Description

The plan will provide data on developing a tissue-engineered scaffold produced by electrospinning with transplantable β cells for treating diabetes mellitus.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Advancing Immune Defense of Pancreatic β -Cells through Innovative Tissue Engineering Scaffolds. (Izp-2024/1-0135)

Researchers

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Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Advancing Immune Defense of Pancreatic β -Cells through Innovative Tissue Engineering Scaffolds

Description:

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Volodymyr Deineka (0000-0002-9492-8170)

Organizations:

University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Advancing Immune Defense of Pancreatic β -Cells through Innovative Tissue Engineering Scaffolds. (Izp-2024/1-0135)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-04-01

4. Templates

Descriptions

Characterization of a electrospun biopolymer scaffold

Detailed physical and biological characterization of a new electrospun scaffold containing a suspension of β -cells and endothelial cells for qualitative and quantitative assessment of viability and activity in vitro for biomedical purposes will open new perspectives in tissue engineering and medicine.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of data collection/generation in this project is to develop and evaluate an innovative tissue-engineered scaffold for pancreatic β -cell transplantation. This scaffold aims to enhance β -cell survival and function while providing protection against immune attacks, ultimately contributing to improved diabetes treatment. The data will originate from experiments involving material synthesis, cell viability assessments, scaffold characterization, immune response evaluations, and in vitro functional studies of β -cells in different conditions.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF

- PNG
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We are going to use only your experimental data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

For other researchers who work in developing tissue-engineered scaffolds or new biomaterials are needed.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

It is not possible for our research.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

-

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Microsoft Excel, GraphPad Prizm, Origin Pro, R.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected date in table format in xlsx or scv format.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Volodymyr Deineka (0000-0002-9492-8170)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall

- Passwords
- Physical access control

The data will separately storage on the working computer in office, on the working computer in laboratory and on the One Drive of working account.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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